

DOI: 10.31866/2617-2674.5.1.2022.257182

**ZASPA, I., BEZRUCHKO, O. PHOTO ART PROJECT
"FEMALE MULTI-COMPONENT ASSOCIATIVE IMAGE
'FERN FLOWER'". PART 2****Iryna Zaspa^{1a}, Oleksandr Bezruchko^{2a}**

¹ PhD Student of the Speciality 034 Culturology,
Master of Audiovisual Arts and Production;

e-mail: duymovochkaira@gmail.com; ORCID: 0000-0003-0648-1901

² Doctor of Study of Art, PhD in Cinematographic Art, Television, Professor;

e-mail: oleksandr_bezruchko@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0001-8360-9388

^a Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Kyiv, Ukraine

**ФОТОМИСТЕЦЬКИЙ ПРОЄКТ «ЖІНОЧИЙ
БАГАТОКОМПОНЕНТНИЙ АСОЦІАТИВНИЙ ОБРАЗ
"ЦВІТ ПАПОРОТІ"». ЧАСТИНА 2****Ірина Заспа^{1a}, Олександр Безручко^{2a}**

¹ аспірантка спеціальності 034 «Культурологія»,
магістр аудіовізуального мистецтва та виробництва;

e-mail: duymovochkaira@gmail.com; ORCID: 0000-0003-0648-1901

² доктор мистецтвознавства, професор;

e-mail: oleksandr_bezruchko@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0001-8360-9388

^a Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв, Київ, Україна

The author's idea. The idea of the second part of the presented photographic project has the same deep main meaning as the first part with the addition of figurative meanings. The comparison of such polar concepts as the beauty of alive and inanimate and revealing them through the female image, which is the basis, gives the opportunity to rethink these concepts. Counterweight of the destructive and at the same time creative processes in the abandoned building, which are reflected in the living plants of the fern and the girl herself, are combined into one whole.

The second part of this photo art project begins with a photo diptych called "Feel", which encourages you to track your own feelings while observing the work. It plays the role of a vocation that permeates the entire series of photographic projects. We consider that any work of art without human comprehension is only a set of certain qualities. As an example, a picture is a set of harmoniously combined spots and lines. Each person endows the experienced images with a special set of qualities selected through their own prism of worldview. Thus, the image can acquire many meanings in the outlined subject.

The presented series broadcasts the heroine's experience of a small life in the walls of dilapidated rooms through her dance, changing poses, movement and her interaction with space. Even the presence of a living person in an abandoned house fills him with life. Another invigorating symbol here is plants and flowers. The question of who this heroine is, the soul of the building, or flowers, or life itself, remains open.

If we turn to the irrational field of the philosophy which is "philosophy of life", we will understand that everything that exists in it is considered as a form of manifestation of "life". Life itself is considered to be the primary holistic reality. Thus, it is possible to draw parallels between the idea of contrasting the animate and the inanimate, abandoned that is displayed in the project with the "philosophy of life", in the understanding of which life opposes the inanimate and can be understood on an intuitive level. The photographic project focuses on the intuitive perception, comprehension and experience of the presented images.

The girl in the frame is a part of this environment and at the same time remains separated from it. This separation is dictated by the abandonment of the building. This abandonment provides opportunities for the perception of the image of the protagonist as a manifestation of "higher powers", which is often represented in the image of an angel. The hint of the supernatural origin of the female image is the elements of clothing, which in some shots are complemented by the presence of wings. Another important building aspect in the created image is the light, which reinforces the above-described symbolism of certain images. The idea of the work within the provided limits allows to interpret the image, which is symbolically called the "fern flower" in the imagination and perception of everyone. In this way, against the background of a terribly beautiful environment, the "fern flower" contains the symbolism of the magical, heavenly and living, real, which exists here and now.

Ukrainian-English translation –

Troian Ivan, e-mail: ivan.troian95@gmail.com

Photographer of the project –

Oleksandr Tverdokhlib, e-mail: icess69@gmail.com

Diptych photo No. 1

**“Feeling” of the
Photo Art Project
“Female Multi-Component
Associative Image
“Fern Flower”**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

105 mm | F1.41 | ISO 400 | 1/350 s

**Images No. 1 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance editing
- Color correction

Light scheme

Light source: natural light
from the window.

Photo No. 2

"Portrait with hydrangeas in hands" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower"

80

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

105 mm | F1.41 | ISO 400 | 1/400 s

**Image No. 2 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance, exposure editing
- Color correction

Light scheme

Light source: natural light
from the window.

Triptych photo No. 3

**"Ballet in an Empty Room" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower"**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

35 mm | F1.41 | ISO 800 | 1/400 s

**Images No. 3 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance editing
- Color correction

Light scheme

Light source: natural light
from the window.

Diptych photo No. 4

82

**"Portrait of a Fern Flower"
of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component
Associative Image
"Fern Flower"**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

105 mm | F1.41 | ISO 800 | 1/350 s

Images No. 4 editing with

Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance, contrast and saturation editing
- Color correction

Light scheme

Light source: natural light
from the window.

Diptych photo No. 5

**"Shined" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower"**

Camera / Lens
Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:
105 mm | F1.41 | ISO 800 | 1/350 s

**Images No. 5 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance editing
- Colour correction

Light scheme
Light source: natural light
from the window.

Diptych photo No. 6

84

**"Light and Shadow" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower"**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

105 mm | F1.41 | ISO 800 | 1/400 s

Images No. 6 editing with

Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance editing
- Color correction

Light scheme

Light source: natural light
from the window.

Diptych photo No. 7

**"Sunlight" of the
Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component
Associative Image
"Fern Flower"**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

35 mm | F1.41 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

**Images No. 7 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance, exposure, contrast and saturation editing
- Color correction

Light scheme

Light source: natural light
from the window.

Photo No. 8

"Movement" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower"

86

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

35 mm | F1.41 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

**Image No. 8 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance, exposure, contrast and saturation editing
- Color correction

Light scheme

Light source: natural light
from the window.

Photo No. 9

**"Manifestation
of higher powers"
of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component
Associative Image
"Fern Flower"**

87

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

35 mm | F1.41 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

**Image No. 9 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance, exposure, contrast and saturation editing
- Color correction

Light scheme

Light source: natural light
from the window.

This is an open access journal and all published articles are licensed under a Creative Commons «Attribution» 4.0.